

EXAMINING THE COMPLEMENTARY ROLE OF SPEAKERS' PERSPECTIVE IN LANGUAGE ATTITUDES RESEARCH: A CASE STUDY OF SAUDI ARABIAN DIALECTS

Laila Mobarak Alhazmi

Asst. Prof., Department of English, College of Science and Arts, King Abdulaziz University, Rabigh, SAUDI ARABIA, lmalhazmi@kau.edu.sa

Abstract

This study investigates the language attitudes of Saudi Arabian dialect speakers towards their own dialects and compares them to previous studies on listeners' attitudes. It addresses the limited attention given to speakers' language attitudes in Saudi Arabia and explores the influence of social background on these attitudes. A language attitudes questionnaire was used as the primary research tool, and 254 Saudi participants representing diverse backgrounds were recruited. The findings reveal that the perceptions of Najdi and urban Bedouin Hijazi dialects align with previous research, while the eastern dialect shows some variations. Najdi speakers perceive their own dialect as the most prestigious, urban Bedouin Hijazi speakers view their dialect as linguistically correct, and eastern participants associate their dialect with friendliness. These characteristics reflect evaluative dimensions in language attitudes such as dynamism, status, and solidarity. The study highlights the importance of considering speakers' perceptions in language attitudes research, as they reveal consistent patterns that align with listeners' perceptions. It also uncovers a previously undisclosed aspect of solidarity with the eastern dialect. These findings emphasize the significance of speakers' perspectives in understanding language attitudes and provide valuable insights into dialect perceptions in Saudi Arabia.

Keywords: language attitudes, speaker's perspective, Saudi dialects.

1 INTRODUCTION

Language attitudes (LAs) have exerted a substantial influence on language usage, variation, evolution, language replacement, and language preservation (Garrett, 2010; Kircher & Zipp, 2022; Sallabank, 2013). LAs encompasses the scientific examination of evaluative reactions to language, which can be elicited by exploring attitudes towards the language itself or attitudes towards the language speaker (Dragojevic et al., 2021).

Previous studies predominantly focused on eliciting language attitudes from listeners, particularly their attitudes towards a language or its speakers. Notably, attitudes towards the language and its speakers yielded similar and correlated findings regarding the language and its speakers (Giles, 1970; Huygens & Vaughan, 1983; Lambert et al., 1960). However, it is crucial to explore the perspectives of language

speakers regarding their own language. Research investigating the inner circle attitudes of speakers towards their languages or dialects could potentially yield similar findings to studies that have examined outer circle attitudes among listeners. This raises the question of how research on speaker perception complements previous research on listener perception. While extensive research has focused on listeners' attitudes towards speakers of specific languages, studies on the speaker's perception of their own dialects or languages have been relatively limited (Derwing, 2003; Gluszek & Dovidio, 2010a, 2010b).

To provide a comprehensive understanding of speaker perception in research, it is important to clarify its meaning. Speaker perception refers to the investigation of speakers' attitudes of themselves when using their language or dialect. In contrast, listener attitudes involve participants providing their attitudes towards specific language based on real voice samples of the language in question. Given the substantial contributions of LAs research to the understanding of language use, language maintenance, and language variation and change, this paper aims to examine the attitudes of Saudi Arabian speakers towards their dialects and compare them with previous studies that focused on listener attitudes towards other speakers.

This study employs direct methods from LAs research, utilizing a language attitudes questionnaire as the primary research tool. The study involves the recruitment of 254 Saudi participants who came from various social backgrounds. The findings contribute to the field of LA research in two significant ways. Firstly, they reveal a consistent language attitude pattern towards central and western dialects in SA, which aligns with findings from previous studies examining listener attitudes in SA. Secondly, a discrepancy in attitudes towards the eastern dialect emerges between listener attitudes in previous studies and speaker attitudes in the current study. This suggests that eliciting speaker attitudes may unveil more latent and concealed attitudes. However, this study serves as a preliminary investigation, and further research is necessary to delve into the reasons behind the emergence of a consistent pattern with certain dialects and a different pattern with another Saudi dialect.

2 SAUDI DIALECTS; AN OVERVIEW

This section provides a succinct overview of the social and historical background of Saudi dialects. The Najdi dialect, which is predominantly spoken in the central region of SA known as Najd, holds historical and political significance. Najd was the first region occupied by King Abdulaziz Al-Saud, the founder of Saudi Arabia, during his efforts to unify the entire Kingdom. Thus, this region holds significance due to its association with the King's conquest and the subsequent unification process. (Al-Rojaie, 2021).

In the region of Hijaz in western Saudi Arabia, the sociolinguistic significance lies in the variation of dialects spoken. Specifically, two distinct dialects are utilized by various social groups residing within the same geographical area, including the region, city, or even specific locations. The urban Bedouin Hijazi (UBH) dialect, also referred to as the tribal Hijazi dialect, is employed by Bedouin groups who were originally inhabitants of rural areas in Hijaz but subsequently migrated to urban centers such as Makkah, Jeddah, and Al-Madina due to economic transformations. In contrast, the Hadari Hijazi dialect represents the dialect spoken by all settlers in Hijaz, irrespective of their origins or ethnic backgrounds. Despite the heterogeneous nature of the settler group, they have developed a dialect that is mutually intelligible, reflecting their shared sense of identity (Alhazmi, 2017; Al-Jehani, 1990; Al-Jehani, 1985; Nahedh, 1989).

The dialect predominant in the southwestern part of Saudi Arabia, which shares a border with Yemen, is the southern dialect. This specific region encompasses territories such as Asir, Tihama, and Jazan. Conversely, the northern dialect is spoken in the sparsely populated northern region of Saudi Arabia (Anishchenkova, 2020). Lastly, the eastern region, situated along the coastal area adjacent to the Arabian Gulf, shares borders with several Arabian Gulf countries, including Qatar, Bahrain, the UAE, and Kuwait. The dialect spoken in the eastern region is occasionally referred to as the Gulf dialect, as it is perceived to be a fusion of various Arabian Gulf dialects (Holes, 1990).

3 THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES ON LANGUAGE ATTITUDES

The theoretical model widely employed for studying language attitudes is the tripartite model, as described by Garrett (2010) and Garrett et al. (2003). This model comprises three components: cognition, affect, and behavior. The cognition component pertains to an individual's perception of an attitude object, specifically a language, and how it is ascribed certain attributes through stereotyping. Various research methods have been used to investigate the cognitive aspect of language attitudes, ranging from direct approaches such as conceptual analysis and direct questioning of participants to indirect methods, including the matched guise technique and its variants. The affect component focuses on the emotional responses elicited by a language,

which can be measured through physiological indicators like “heart rate, galvanic skin response or by collecting verbal reports of feelings or mood” (Breckler, 1985, p. 1191). The behavior component analyzes the actions exhibited towards a language, which can be assessed through verbal statements and overt behaviors. In this study, I will specifically explore the cognition component of language attitudes among Saudi speakers towards their dialects using direct questions. This is crucial for understanding the beliefs and thoughts of Saudi speakers about their language, which may range from favorable to unfavorable perceptions.

3.1. Previous Research On Language Attitudes

Previous research on language attitudes, particularly in relation to listeners' perceptions of speech, has identified three main dimensions through which attitudes are often expressed: status, solidarity, and dynamism (Garrett, 2010, p. 55). The status dimension reflects the perception of a language and its speakers as prestigious, educated, correct, and standard. The solidarity dimension encompasses ratings of the language and its speakers as friendly, kind, and morally upright. The dynamism dimension involves characterizations of the language and its speakers as being energetic, enthusiastic, and confident (Garret, 2010). Numerous studies on language attitudes consistently found that high-prestige varieties are associated with the status dimension, while low-prestige varieties are linked to the solidarity dimension (Dragojevic et al., 2018; Preston, 1989). Recent research has also shown that neo-standard varieties and those spoken in fast growing societies tend to be associated with the dynamism dimension (Alhazmi, 2023; Kristiansen, 2009). Considering the significant impact of language attitudes research on understanding how participants perceive dialects and how such perceptions reflect social structures within societies, this study will investigate the characteristics of Saudi speakers' own dialects from their own perspectives.

3.2. Previous research on language attitudes research in SA

Previous research has examined the sociolinguistic aspects of regional dialects in Saudi Arabia (SA). SA, being a large country with diverse cultures and dialects, primarily uses Arabic as its main language. Previous studies have identified five main dialects spoken in different regions of the country: Najdi dialect, northern dialect, southern dialect, eastern dialect, and Hijazi dialect (Al-Rojaie, 2020). Regarding the Hijazi dialect, researchers have argued that the linguistic situation in Hijaz differs from other regions due to a dichotomous linguistic divide within the region, which is more social and ethnic in nature. The dialects in the Hijazi region can be classified as urban Bedouin Hijazi and Hadari Hijazi (Alhazmi, 2018; Al-Jehani, 1990; Omar, 1975). Consequently, this paper aims to investigate the four regional dialects in SA, along with the two social dialects in Hijaz, thereby examining a total of six dialects from the perspectives of their speakers.

Research on LAs in SA is still in its early stages, with most studies being introductory in nature. To the best of my knowledge, no study has explored speakers' perspectives on their dialects; instead, previous research has primarily focused on listeners' perceptions. For instance, a study conducted by Alhazmi (2023) examined listeners' attitudes towards four dialects in SA, namely Najdi, eastern, northern, and southern dialects, using verbal guise techniques (VGT). Alhazmi's study identified three main attitudinal dimensions: dynamism-status, dynamism-language, and solidarity. The study found that the Najdi dialect strongly reflected the dynamism dimension, while the southern dialects exhibited a strong association with the Solidarity dimension. In the present study, I will select one characteristic from each dimension identified in Alhazmi's study (2023). By doing so, the study aims to investigate whether any similarities exist between listeners' perceptions (as previously investigated by Alhazmi in 2023) and speakers' perceptions (the focus of the current study). The three characteristics chosen from Alhazmi's study to represent the attitudinal dimensions in the current study are: prestigious (representing the dynamism dimension), correct (representing the status dimension), and friendly (representing the Solidarity dimension). Notably, previous studies have associated 'prestigious' with the status dimension (El-Dash & Busnardo, 2001; Genesee & Holobow, 1989), while in Alhazmi's study (2023), conducted in a Saudi context, 'prestigious' emerged within the dynamism dimension. Therefore, in this study, 'prestigious' will be utilized as an indicator of the dynamism dimension.

Similarly, Al-Hakami (2023) investigated listeners' perception of three regional dialects in SA: Qassimi dialect (a sub-dialect of Najdi dialect), Hasawi dialect (a sub-dialect of eastern dialect), and Jizani dialect (a sub-dialect of southern dialect). Al-Hakami's study revealed three main dimensions: solidarity, status, and aesthetic. The Jizani dialect exhibited a strong association with the Solidarity dimension, while the Hasawi dialect demonstrated a strong connection with both the status and Aesthetic dimensions. Previous studies have indicated that the dimensions identified and their associations with SA dialects reflect social structuring based on LAs. Thus, the present study aims to explore speakers' perspectives and how they can

complement previous studies on listeners' perspectives, providing a more comprehensive and broader understanding of attitudes in SA.

Considering the significant impact of LAs on listeners' perceptions and the dialect diversity in SA, the present study will investigate speakers' perspectives by addressing the following research questions:

RQ1: How do Saudi speakers characterize their spoken dialect? Are there any similarities between speakers' perspectives in this study and listeners' perspectives in previous studies?

RQ2: How do participants' social backgrounds influence the results?

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1. Method

The research employed a questionnaire as its primary instrument, utilizing a direct approach in the form of direct questioning, where dialect names were conceptually represented. The use of a direct approach in questionnaires is widely acknowledged in LAs research and has been proven successful (Garrett et al., 2009; Giles, 1970).

The questionnaire was divided into two sections: the first section gathered information about the participants' social background, while the second part aimed to elicit attitudes toward characteristics of Saudi dialects. The questionnaire utilized a Likert scale to present the characteristics, allowing respondents to indicate their level of agreement on a scale of 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

4.2. Participants

The study involves the recruitment of 254 Saudi participants who came from various social backgrounds. Table 1 presents the distribution of participants based on their self-identified regional dialects, genders, ages, and educational levels.

Characteristic		n	%
Dialect			
	southern dialect	46	18.1
	northern dialect	10	3.9
	Najdi dialect	66	26.0
	eastern dialect	23	9.1
	urban Bedouin Hijazi dialect	43	16.9
	Hadari Hijazi dialect	66	26.0
Gender			
	Male	27	10.6
	Female	227	89.4
Age			
	18–24	20	7.9
	25–34	35	13.8
	35–44	87	34.3
	45–54	76	29.9
	55–64	34	13.4
	Over 65	2	.8
Level of education			
	Secondary	33	13.0
	Undergraduate	166	65.4
	Postgraduate	55	21.7

4.3. Procedures

The online survey was conducted in November 2023 through popular social networks such as Twitter and WhatsApp. The study aimed to include Saudis residing both within Saudi Arabia and abroad.

4.4. Statistical analysis

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS software, version 28. The analysis encompassed descriptive statistics and ANOVA.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Characteristics of Saudi dialects from the speaker's perspective

This section addresses research question 1 by examining how each Saudi speaker in the study rated their dialect in relation to the three characteristics, with each characteristic rated on a scale from 1 to 5 (see Table 2).

Table 2: Means and standard deviations of Saudi speakers' attitudes toward the characteristics of their dialects (1=strongly agree, 5=strongly disagree).

Participant' spoken dialect		When I speak with my dialect, I think others perceive me as a prestigious person	When I speak with my dialect, I believe others consider my dialect as the most correct in SA.	When I speak with my dialect, I believe others see my dialect as the friendliest in SA
southern dialect	Mean	3.02	2.51	2.48
	N	46	46	46
	Std. Deviation	1.000	1.019	1.027
northern dialect	Mean	3.80	3.30	2.30
	N	10	10	10
	Std. Deviation	.919	.675	1.160
Najdi dialect	Mean	2.77	2.59	2.41
	N	66	66	66
	Std. Deviation	.989	.960	.976
eastern dialect	Mean	3.00	2.96	2.26
	N	23	23	23
	Std. Deviation	1.168	1.107	1.096
urban Bedouin Hijazi dialect	Mean	3.19	2.37	2.44
	N	43	43	43
	Std. Deviation	.982	1.009	.959
Hadari Hijazi dialect	Mean	2.82	2.91	2.29
	N	66	66	66
	Std. Deviation	.893	1.003	.855

The findings regarding attitudes toward dialect characteristics indicate that Najdi, urban Bedouin Hijazi, and eastern participants reported more positive views toward their dialects compared to the Hadari Hijazi, southern, and northern participant groups. Specifically, Najdi speakers believed that others perceive their dialect as the most prestigious, while participants from the northern region rated themselves the least prestigious. Moreover, urban Bedouin Hijazi speakers rated their dialect as the most linguistically correct in SA, whereas participants from the northern region rated their dialect as the least correct. Finally, participants from the eastern region considered their dialect as the friendliest in SA, whereas those from the southern region rated their dialects as the least friendly among Saudi dialects.

Regarding the impact of social background, the dialect of the speaker was the only factor that yielded significant results. A significance level of $p < .020$ was observed in relation to the perception of the first characteristic "prestigious" on the scale (see Table 3). Post-hoc comparisons using the Tukey HSD test indicated that participants whose dialect was northern rated their own dialects higher compared to those whose dialects were Najdi and Hadari Hijazi (see Table 4). It is important to note that higher mean scores indicate less agreement with the dialect being perceived as prestigious, with the scale ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

Table 3: Effects of speakers' own dialect on the results.

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	13.107	5	2.621	2.726	.020
Within Groups	238.499	248	.962		
Total	251.606	253			

Table 4: Post-hoc test results on the dialect demographic variable

Spoken dialect (1)	Spoken dialect (2)	Mean difference	Std. Error	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound
northern dialect	Najdi dialect	1.027*	.333	.027	.07	1.98
	Hadari Hijazi dialect	.982*	.333	.040	.03	1.94

6 DISCUSSION

This section examines the perceptions of Saudi speakers regarding the association of dynamism, status, and Solidarity dimensions with Saudi Arabian dialects. The research question aims to uncover how the speakers characterize the dialects in question. Three characteristics representing attitudinal dimensions were selected from the Saudi language attitudes literature. The findings indicate that Najdi participants had higher scores in relation to the characteristic representing the dynamism dimension, which is considered prestigious. Bedouin Hijazi participants had higher scores in relation to the characteristic representing the status dimension, which is perceived as 'correct'. eastern participants had higher scores in relation to the characteristic representing the solidarity dimension, which is seen as 'friendly'. The influence of social factors suggests that the speaker's dialect has the most significant effect in the study, with Najdi dialect speakers having more positive perceptions of their dialect as prestigious compared to northern dialect speakers.

Overall, the findings reveal a structured pattern in language attitudes in Saudi Arabia, with Najdi, Hijazi Bedouin, and eastern dialects being strongly associated with the three dimensions, while the northern and southern dialects emerged less strongly. This finding can be understood by considering the background of Saudi Arabian dialects. The emergence of the Najdi dialect in the dynamism dimension can be attributed to

the political importance of Najdi, which contributes to its perception as the most prestigious dialect in the Arabian Peninsula. Previous studies have reported similar findings, such as the study by Alhazmi and Alfalg (2022), which used the keyword technique to investigate language attitudes and found that Najdi dialect is regarded as 'prestigious' in Saudi Arabia. Additionally, Alhazmi (2023) revealed that the Najdi dialect strongly aligns with the dynamism dimension. In summary, the present study, which explores speakers' perceptions, yielded similar results to previous studies that examined listeners' perceptions, particularly in terms of perceiving the Najdi dialect as the most prestigious in Saudi Arabia.

Regarding the Bedouin Hijazi dialect, the dichotomous situation arises from the fact that urban Bedouin Hijazi speakers perceive their dialect as the most correct among other dialects. This perception can be ascribed to simultaneous presence of their dialect alongside an alternate dialect utilized by early settlers who established themselves in the Hijaz region approximately two centuries ago. Urban Bedouins tend to convey a message of linguistic security by scoring high in the 'correct' characteristic. Similar findings were reported in a study by Alhazmi (2018), which found that the urban Bedouin dialect prominently aligns with the 'traditional' dimension. The 'traditional' dimension shares several characteristics with the status dimension, one of which is 'correct'.

Regarding the eastern dialect, its speakers perceive it as the friendliest in Saudi Arabia. Previous research has indicated that the characteristic 'friendly' is indicative of the solidarity dimension (Garrett, 2010). Kircher and Zipp (2022) mention that a language variety that receives a favorable assessment in terms of solidarity evokes emotions of connection and inclusion. It is important to note that this finding contradicts the findings of a previous study on listeners' language attitudes by Alhazmi (2023), which revealed the eastern dialect as the least dialect associated with the solidarity dimension. This suggests that speakers' perceptions cannot be isolated from listeners' perceptions, as the former yielded unexpected findings that warrant further investigation.

One limitation of the study is the imbalance in the number of participants among dialect groups, particularly with significantly fewer northern dialect speakers compared to other dialect speakers in Saudi Arabia. Every effort was made to distribute the questionnaire across various platforms to reach a larger and more balanced number of participants, but unfortunately, the percentage of northern speakers' participants was only 3.9% of the entire sample. Therefore, it is not possible to claim that the findings of the study can be generalized due to the imbalance among dialect speakers. The current research recommends a broader study on language attitudes that includes perspectives from both listeners and speakers, with a larger number of participants and balanced demographic groups.

7 CONCLUSION

This study revealed speaker's perceptions towards SA dialects has emerged in similar pattern to listener's perception revealed in previous studies. The study revealed that although the language attitudes elicitation were altered from listeners to speakers, the perceptions toward Najdi and urban Bedouin Hijazi revealed similar pattern while the perceptions toward eastern dialect recorded some changes. Thus, finding would indicate two things; first speakers' perceptions cannot be ignored in LAs research as it reveals homogenous language attitudes pattern that is revealed by both speakers and listeners perceptions in regard to the Bedouin and Najdi dialects. Second, speakers' perception revealed yet another facet of solidarity with the eastern dialect that was not revealed in previous studies that focused merely on the listeners perceptions.

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